

Supplementary Tables titles

Table S1. Loadings for PCA reducing dimensionality of body and bill size

Table S2. Output of the brms models where we tested for differences in body and bill size across colonisations

Table S3. Full dataset containing information about the samples

Table S4. Associated loci with body size variation for which there is significant intrapopulation variation

Table S5. Genotype information for the highest associated locus for body and bill size

Table S6. Annotated genes associated with body size variation

Table S7. Associated loci with bill size variation for which there is significant intrapopulation variation

Table S8. Annotated genes associated with bill size variation

Table S9. Narrow-sense heritability estimates

Table S10. Annotated genes within inversions